

Cubic H-ideals in BCK-Algebras

¹B. Satyanarayana and ²U. Bindu Madhavi

¹Department of Mathematics, Acharya Nagarjuna University
Nagarjuna Nagar-522 510, A.P. India.

E-mail: drbsn63@yahoo.co.in

²Department of Mathematics, Krishna University P.G Centre
Nuzvid-521 201, A.P., India.

E-mail: bindumadhavi@gmail.com

Abstract: The notions of cubic H-ideals of BCK-algebras are introduced and several related properties are investigated.

Keywords: BCK-algebras; cubic sets; cubic H-ideals.

1. INTRODUCTION AND PRELIMINAREIS

The study of BCK-algebras was initiated by Iseki in 1966 as a generalization of the concept of set-theoretic difference and propositional calculus, after, a large volume of literature has been produced on the theory of BCK-algebras. The concept of fuzzy sets were introduced by Zadeh in 1965, several researchers explored the generalization of the notion of fuzzy sets. The notion of interval-valued fuzzy sets were first introduced by Zadeh as an extension of fuzzy sets. Based on the interval valued fuzzy sets, Jun et al. [6] introduced the notion of cubic sets. Zhan and Tan [3] introduced the fuzzy H-ideals in BCK-algebras.

In this paper we introduce the concept of cubic H-ideals and investigate some of its properties.

A BCK-algebra is a non-empty set X with a binary operation $*$ and a constant 0 satisfying the following axioms:

$$(1). (x * y) * (x * z) \leq (z * y)$$

$$(2). x * (x * y) \leq y,$$

$$(3). x \leq x,$$

$$(4). x \leq y \text{ and } y \leq x \text{ imply } x = y,$$

$$(5). 0 \leq x \text{ for all } x \text{ in } X.$$

A BCK-algebra can be partially ordered by $x \leq y \Leftrightarrow x * y = 0$ this ordering is called BCK-ordering. The following statements are true in a BCK-algebra:

$$(a) x * 0 = x, \quad (b) (x * y) * z \leq (x * z) * y, \quad (c) x * y \leq x$$

$$(d) (x * y) * z \leq (x * z) * (y * z), \quad (e) x \leq y \Rightarrow x * z \leq y * z \text{ and } z * y \leq z * x.$$

Definition 1.1:[7] A Subset I of a BCK-algebra $(X, *, 0)$ is called an ideal of X , for any $x, y \in X$.

$$I_1. 0 \in I,$$

$$I_2. x * y \text{ and } y \in I \Rightarrow x \in I.$$

Definition 1.2:[7] An ideal I of a BCK-algebra $(X, *, 0)$ is called closed if

$$I_3. 0 * x \in I, \text{ for all } x \in I.$$

Definition 1.3:[7] A non empty subset I of a BCK-algebra X is called a H-ideal of X , if it satisfies I_1 and I_4 .

$$x * (y * z) \in I \text{ and } y \in I \Rightarrow x * z \in I.$$

Definition 1.4:[7] A fuzzy subset H in a BCK-algebra X is called fuzzy H-ideal of X , if

$$(FH-1). \mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$$

$$(FH-2). \mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\} \quad \forall x, y, z \in X.$$

The fuzzy set μ in X is called fuzzy sub algebra of X , if $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for $x, y \in X$.

Definition 1.5:[7] For fuzzy sets μ and λ of X and $s, t \in [0, 1]$. The sets $U(\mu; t) = \{x \in X : \mu(x) \geq t\}$ is called upper t -level cut of μ and $L(\lambda; s) = \{x \in X : \lambda(x) \leq s\}$ is called lower s -level cut of λ . Let X be the collection of objects denoted generally by x . Then the fuzzy set A in X is defined as $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x)) : x \in X\}$ where $\mu_A(x)$ is called the membership value of x in A and $0 \leq \mu_A(x) \leq 1$.

Now we recall the concept of interval-valued fuzzy sets:

By the interval number D we mean an interval $[a^-, a^+]$ where $0 \leq a^- \leq a^+ \leq 1$. For interval numbers $D_1 = [a_1^-, b_1^+]$, $D_2 = [a_2^-, b_2^+]$. We define

- $\text{Min}(D_1, D_2) = D_1 \cap D_2 = \min\{[a_1^-, b_1^+], [a_2^-, b_2^+]\}$
 $= [\min\{a_1^-, a_2^-\}, \min\{b_1^+, b_2^+\}]$
- $\text{Max}(D_1, D_2) = D_1 \cup D_2 = \max\{[a_1^-, b_1^+], [a_2^-, b_2^+]\}$
 $= [\max\{a_1^-, a_2^-\}, \max\{b_1^+, b_2^+\}]$
- $D_1 + D_2 = [a_1^- + a_2^- - a_1^- \cdot a_2^-, b_1^+ + b_2^+ - b_1^+ \cdot b_2^+]$

And put

- $D_1 \leq D_2 \Leftrightarrow a_1^- \leq a_2^- \text{ and } b_1^+ \leq b_2^+$
- $D_1 = D_2 \Leftrightarrow a_1^- = a_2^- \text{ and } b_1^+ = b_2^+$
- $D_1 < D_2 \Leftrightarrow D_1 \leq D_2 \text{ and } D_1 \neq D_2$
- $mD = m[a_1^-, b_1^+] = [ma_1^-, mb_1^+]$, where $0 \leq m \leq 1$.

An interval valued fuzzy set A over X is an object having the form $A = \{(x, \tilde{\mu}_A) : x \in X\}$ where $\tilde{\mu}_A(x) : X \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ is the set of all sub-intervals of $[0, 1]$. The interval $\tilde{\mu}_A(x)$ denotes the intervals of the degree of membership of element x to the set A where $\tilde{\mu}_A(x) = [\mu_A^-(x), \mu_A^+(x)]$ for all $x \in X$.

The determination of maximum and minimum between two real numbers is very simple but it is not simple for two intervals. Biswas [5] described a method to find max/sup and min/inf between two intervals or set of intervals.

Definition 1.6:[5] Consider two elements $D_1, D_2 \in D[0,1]$. If $D_1 = [a_1^-, a_1^+]$ and $D_2 = [a_2^-, a_2^+]$ then $rmin(D_1, D_2) = [\min(a_1^-, a_2^-), \min(a_1^+, a_2^+)]$ which is denoted by $D_1 \wedge D_2$. Thus if $D_i = [a_i^-, a_i^+] \in D[0,1]$ for $i = 1, 2, 3 \dots$ then we define $r sup_i(D_i) = [\sup_i(a_i^-), \sup_i(a_i^+)]$ i.e., $\forall_i D_i = [\vee_i a_i^-, \vee_i a_i^+]$. Now we call $D_1 \geq D_2$ iff $a_1^- \geq a_2^-$ and $a_1^+ \geq a_2^+$. Similarly, the relations $D_1 \leq D_2$ and $D_1 = D_2$ are defined.

Based on (interval valued) fuzzy sets, Jun et al.[9] introduced the notion of (internal, external) cubic sets and investigated several properties.

Definition 1.7:[6] Let X be a non-empty set. A cubic set A in X is a Structure $A = \{(x, \tilde{\mu}_A(x), \lambda_A(x)) ; x \in X\}$ which is briefly denoted by $A = (\tilde{\mu}_A, \lambda_A)$ where $\tilde{\mu}_A = [\mu_A^-, \mu_A^+]$ is an interval valued fuzzy set in X and λ_A is fuzzy set in X .

2. Cubic H-ideals of BCK-algebras

Let X denotes a BCK-algebra unless otherwise specified. Combined the definitions of fuzzy H-ideal over a crisp set and the idea of cubic set we define cubic fuzzy H-ideal. After that, we give some important consequences of this representation

Definition 2.1: Let $A = (\tilde{\mu}_A, \lambda_A)$ be a cubic set in X , where X is a BCK-algebra, then the set A is cubic H-ideal of X if,

$$(CH-1). \tilde{\mu}_A(0) \geq \tilde{\mu}_A(x) \text{ and } \lambda_A(0) \leq \lambda_A(x)$$

$$(CH-2). \tilde{\mu}_A(x * z) \geq rmin\{\tilde{\mu}_A(x * (y * z)), \tilde{\mu}_A(y)\}$$

$$(CH-3). \lambda_A(x * z) \leq max\{\lambda_A(x * (y * z)), \lambda_A(y)\} \text{ for all } x, y, z \in X.$$

Example 2.2 Let $X = \{0, x, y, z\}$ be a BCK-algebra with the following Cayley table

*	0	x	y	z
0	0	0	0	0
x	x	0	0	0
y	y	x	0	0
z	z	y	x	0

We define a cubic set $A = (X, \tilde{\mu}_A, \lambda_A)$ by $\tilde{\mu}_A(0) = \tilde{\mu}_A(x) = [0.6, 0.7]$,

$$\tilde{\mu}_A(y) = \tilde{\mu}_A(z) = [0.2, 0.3], \lambda_A(0) = 0.1, \lambda_A(x) = 0.3, \lambda_A(y) = \lambda_A(z) = 0.4$$

By routine calculations we know that $A = (\tilde{\mu}_A, \lambda_A)$ is a cubic H-ideal of X .

Definition 2.3: A cubic set $A = (X, \tilde{\mu}_A, \lambda_A)$ in a BCK-algebra X is called a cubic closed H-ideal if it satisfies the following

$$(CCH-1). \tilde{\mu}_A(0 * x) \geq \tilde{\mu}_A(x) \text{ and } \lambda_A(0 * x) \leq \lambda_A(x)$$

$$(CCH-2). \tilde{\mu}_A(x * z) \geq rmin\{\tilde{\mu}_A(x * (y * z)), \tilde{\mu}_A(y)\}$$

$$(CCH-3). \lambda_A(x * z) \leq max\{\lambda_A(x * (y * z)), \lambda_A(y)\} \text{ for all } x, y, z \in X.$$

Theorem 2.4: Let $A = (X, \tilde{\mu}_A, \lambda_A)$ be a cubic H-ideal of X , if there is a sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X such that

$$(i) \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{\mu}_A(x_n) = [1, 1] \text{ then } \tilde{\mu}_A(0) = [1, 1] \text{ and}$$

$$(ii) \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \lambda_A(x_n) = 0 \text{ then } \lambda_A(0) = 0.$$

Proof: Since $\tilde{\mu}_A(0) \geq \tilde{\mu}_A(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Therefore $\tilde{\mu}_A(0) \geq \tilde{\mu}_A(x_n)$ for every positive integer n.

Consider $[1,1] \geq \tilde{\mu}_A(0) \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{\mu}_A(x_n) = [1,1]$. Hence $\tilde{\mu}_A(0) = [1,1]$.

Since $\lambda_A(0) \leq \lambda_A(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Thus $\lambda_A(0) \leq \lambda_A(x_n)$ for every positive integer n, Now $0 \leq \lambda_A(0) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \lambda_A(x_n) = 0$. Hence $\lambda_A(0) = 0$.

Theorem 2.5: A cubic set $A = (\tilde{\mu}_A, \lambda_A)$ in X is a cubic H-ideal of X if and only if μ_A^-, μ_A^+ and λ_A are fuzzy H-ideals of X.

Proof : Let μ_A^-, μ_A^+ and λ_A are fuzzy H-ideals of X and $x, y, z \in X$. Then

$$\mu_A^-(0) \geq \mu_A^-(x), \mu_A^+(0) \geq \mu_A^+(x), \mu_A^-(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu_A^-(x * (y * z)), \mu_A^-(y)\},$$

$$\mu_A^+(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu_A^+(x * (y * z)), \mu_A^+(y)\} \text{ and } \lambda_A(x * z) \leq \max\{\lambda_A(x * (y * z)), \lambda_A(y)\}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now } \tilde{\mu}_A(x * z) &= [\mu_A^-(x * z), \mu_A^+(x * z)] \\ &\geq [\min\{\mu_A^-(x * (y * z)), \mu_A^-(y)\}, \min\{\mu_A^+(x * (y * z)), \mu_A^+(y)\}] \\ &= r\min\{[\mu_A^-(x * (y * z)), \mu_A^+(x * (y * z))], [\mu_A^-(y), \mu_A^+(y)]\} \\ &= r\min\{\tilde{\mu}_A(x * (y * z)), \tilde{\mu}_A(y)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore A is cubic H-ideal of X.

Conversely assume that A is a cubic H-ideal of X. For any $x, y, z \in X$,

$$\begin{aligned} [\mu_A^-(x * z), \mu_A^+(x * z)] &= \tilde{\mu}_A(x * z) \geq r\min\{\tilde{\mu}_A(x * (y * z)), \tilde{\mu}_A(y)\} \\ &= r\min\{[\mu_A^-(x * (y * z)), \mu_A^+(x * (y * z))], [\mu_A^-(y), \mu_A^+(y)]\} \\ &= [\min\{\mu_A^-(x * (y * z)), \mu_A^-(y)\}, \min\{\mu_A^+(x * (y * z)), \mu_A^+(y)\}] \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\mu_A^-(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu_A^-(x * (y * z)), \mu_A^-(y)\}, \mu_A^+(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu_A^+(x * (y * z)), \mu_A^+(y)\} \text{ and}$$

$$\lambda_A(x * z) \leq \max\{\lambda_A(x * (y * z)), \lambda_A(y)\}.$$

Hence μ_A^-, μ_A^+ and λ_A are fuzzy H-ideals of X.

Theorem2.6: If $A = (X, \tilde{\mu}_A, \lambda_A)$ is cubic H-ideal of a BCK algebra x, then we have the following:

$$x \leq a \implies \tilde{\mu}_A(x) \geq \tilde{\mu}_A(a) \text{ and } \lambda_A(x) \leq \lambda_A(a) \text{ for all } x, a \in X.$$

Proof : Let $x, a \in X$ such that $x \leq a \implies x * a = 0$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } \tilde{\mu}_A(x) &= \tilde{\mu}_A(x * 0) \geq r\min\{\tilde{\mu}_A(x * (a * 0)), \tilde{\mu}_A(a)\} \\ &= r\min\{\tilde{\mu}_A(x * a), \tilde{\mu}_A(a)\} \\ &= r\min\{\tilde{\mu}_A(0), \tilde{\mu}_A(a)\} = \tilde{\mu}_A(a) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } \lambda_A(x) &= \lambda_A(x * 0) \leq \max\{\lambda_A(x * (a * 0)), \lambda_A(a)\} \\ &= \max\{\lambda_A(x * a), \lambda_A(a)\} \\ &= \max\{\lambda_A(0), \lambda_A(a)\} \\ &= \lambda_A(a). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\lambda_A(x) \leq \lambda_A(a)$.

Definition 2.7: Let $A = (\tilde{\mu}_A, \lambda_A)$ be a cubic set in X . For $[s_1, s_2] \in D(0,1)$ and $t \in [0,1]$

The set $U(\tilde{\mu}_A; [s_1, s_2]) = \{x \in X / \tilde{\mu}_A(x) \geq [s_1, s_2]\}$ is called upper $[s_1, s_2]$ level of A and $L(\lambda_A, t) = \{x \in X / \lambda_A(x) \leq t\}$ is called lower t -level cut of A .

Theorem 2.8: If $A = (\tilde{\mu}_A, \lambda_A)$ is a cubic H-ideal of X , then the upper $[s_1, s_2]$ level and lower t -level of A are H-ideals of X .

Proof: Let $x \in U(\tilde{\mu}_A, [s_1, s_2])$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \tilde{\mu}_A(x) &\geq [s_1, s_2] \\ \Rightarrow [s_1, s_2] &\leq \tilde{\mu}_A(x) \leq \tilde{\mu}_A(0) \\ \Rightarrow \tilde{\mu}_A(0) &\geq [s_1, s_2] \\ \Rightarrow 0 &\in U(\tilde{\mu}_A; [s_1, s_2]) \end{aligned}$$

$x * (y * z) \in U(\tilde{\mu}_A; [s_1, s_2]), y \in U(\tilde{\mu}_A; [s_1, s_2])$

$\tilde{\mu}_A(x * (y * z)) \geq [s_1, s_2]$ and $\tilde{\mu}_A(y) \geq [s_1, s_2]$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } \tilde{\mu}_A(x * z) &\geq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{\mu}_A(x * (y * z)), \tilde{\mu}_A(y)\} \\ &\geq \text{rmin}\{[s_1, s_2], [s_1, s_2]\} \\ &= \{\min[s_1, s_1], \min[s_1, s_2]\} \\ &= [s_1, s_2] \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $x * z \in U(\tilde{\mu}_A; [s_1, s_2])$

Hence $U(\tilde{\mu}_A; [s_1, s_2])$ is an H-ideal of X

$$\begin{aligned} \text{For } x \in L(\lambda_A; t) &\Rightarrow \lambda_A(x) \leq t \\ &\Rightarrow \lambda_A(0) \leq \lambda_A(x) \leq t \\ &\Rightarrow 0 \in L(\lambda_A; t) \end{aligned}$$

Let $x * (y * z) \in L(\lambda_A; t)$ and $y \in L(\lambda_A; t)$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda_A(x * (y * z)) \leq t \text{ and } \lambda_A(y) \leq t$$

Since for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_A(x * z) &\leq \max\{\lambda_A(x * (y * z)), \lambda_A(y)\} \\ &\leq \max\{t, t\} = t \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda_A(x * z) \leq t.$$

Therefore $x * z \in L(\lambda_A; t)$ for all $x, y, z \in X$

Hence $L(\lambda_A; t)$ is an H-ideal of x .

3. Homomorphism of cubic H-ideal

Let F be a mapping from a set X into a set Y . Let $B = (\tilde{\mu}_B, \lambda_B)$ be cubic set in y . Then the inverse image of B is defined as $f^{-1}(B) = \{(x, (f^{-1}(\tilde{\mu}_B), f^{-1}(\lambda_B))) / x \in X\}$ with the membership function and non-membership function

respectively are given by $f^{-1}(\tilde{\mu}_B)(x) = \tilde{\mu}_B(f(x))$ and $f^{-1}(\lambda_B)(x) = \lambda_B(f(x))$. It can be shown that $f^{-1}(B)$ is a cubic set.

Theorem 3.1: Let $f: X \rightarrow Y$ be a homomorphism of BCK-algebras. If $B = (\tilde{\mu}_B, \lambda_B)$ is a cubic H-ideal of Y , then the pre image $f^{-1}(B) = \{(x, f^{-1}(\tilde{\mu}_B), f^{-1}(\lambda_B)) / x \in X\}$ of B under f is a cubic H-ideal of X .

Proof: Let $B = (\tilde{\mu}_B, \lambda_B)$ is a cubic H-ideal of Y . Let $x, y, z \in X \Rightarrow f(x), f(y), f(z) \in Y$.

Consider $f^{-1}(\tilde{\mu}_B)(0) = \tilde{\mu}_B(f(0)) \geq \tilde{\mu}_B(f(x)) = f^{-1}(\tilde{\mu}_B)(x)$ and

$$f^{-1}(\lambda_B)(0) = \lambda_B(f(0)) \leq \lambda_B(f(x)) = f^{-1}(\lambda_B)(x)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Thus } f^{-1}(\tilde{\mu}_B)(x * z) &= \tilde{\mu}_B(f(x * z)) \geq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{\mu}_B(f(x * (y * z))), \tilde{\mu}_B(f(y))\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{f^{-1}(\tilde{\mu}_B)(x * (y * z)), f^{-1}(\tilde{\mu}_B)(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } f^{-1}(\lambda_B)(x * z) &= \lambda_B(f(x * z)) \leq \text{max}\{\lambda_B(f(x * (y * z))), \lambda_B(f(y))\} \\ &= \text{max}\{f^{-1}(\lambda_B)(x * (y * z)), f^{-1}(\lambda_B)(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $f^{-1}(B) = \{(x, f^{-1}(\tilde{\mu}_B), f^{-1}(\lambda_B)) / x \in X\}$ is a cubic H-ideal of Y .

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